

Phytochemical Composition and Functional Group Characterization of *Dacryodes edulis* Exudate: Implications for sustainable Industrial Applications

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Abstract

The growing demand for sustainable and environmentally friendly industrial materials has increased interest in plant-derived biomaterials as alternatives to synthetic chemicals. This study investigated the phytochemical composition and functional group characteristics of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate with the aim of evaluating its suitability for sustainable industrial applications. Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analyses were carried out using standard analytical procedures, while Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to identify the functional groups present in the purified exudate. The qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and carbohydrates, whereas anthraquinones were absent. Quantitative analysis showed that carbohydrate had the highest concentration (36.5294 mg/100 g), followed by tannins (0.04789 mg/100 g), flavonoids (0.0397 mg/100 g), alkaloids (0.0208 mg/100 g), phenols (0.0103 mg/100 g), and saponins (0.0090 mg/100 g). FTIR analysis indicated the presence of important functional groups such as hydroxyl (O–H), carbonyl (C=O), alkene (C=C), methylene, and alkane groups at characteristic wave numbers of 3389.5, 1707.1, 1640.0, 3071.3, 2922.2, and 2870.1 cm^{-1} respectively. The findings suggest that *Dacryodes edulis* exudate possesses valuable phytochemical constituents and functional properties that could support its utilization in the production of eco-friendly

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industrial products such as natural inks, adhesives, coatings, bonding and sizing agent in paper and textile industries. The study therefore highlights the potential of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate as a renewable biomaterial for sustainable industrial applications.

Keywords: Exudate, phytochemical, FTIR, functional group, sustainable biomaterial

1.0 Introduction

The increasing global concern over environmental pollution and the depletion of non-renewable resources has intensified the search for sustainable and environmentally friendly materials from natural sources. Plant-derived exudates, gums, and resins are increasingly attracting scientific and industrial interest because of their biodegradability, renewability, low toxicity, and broad industrial applications (Udo *et al.*, 2020). These natural substances are gradually being explored as alternatives to synthetic industrial chemicals that often contribute to environmental contamination and health hazards. Among such promising biomaterials is the exudate obtained from *Dacryodes edulis*, a tropical plant widely distributed in West and Central Africa.

Dacryodes edulis, commonly known as African pear or bush pear, belongs to the family Burseraceae and is highly valued for its nutritional, medicinal, and economic importance (Akpabio, *et al.*, 2012a). The plant produces an exudate rich in bioactive compounds and organic constituents which may possess important industrial properties (Akpabio and Akpakpan. 2012). Plant exudates generally serve as protective secretions against microbial attack, physical injury, and environmental stress, while also containing numerous phytochemicals of biological and industrial relevance (Akpakpan *et al.*, 2017, Sofowora, 1993). These phytochemicals include alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, and carbohydrates, many of which exhibit

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antioxidant, antimicrobial, adhesive, and dye-binding properties (Akpan *et al.*, 2021). The phytochemical composition of plant exudates is influenced not only by genetic factors but also by environmental conditions, including heavy metal contamination (Ubong *et al.*, 2023, Basseyy *et al.*, 2026). If heavy metals are present in the exudate, it will induce oxidative stress in plants through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which stimulate the synthesis of defensive secondary metabolites such as phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids (Sofowora, 1993, Akpan *et al.*, 2017).

In recent years, the principles of sustainable chemistry have encouraged the replacement of petroleum-based and hazardous synthetic materials with renewable plant-based alternatives. Natural biomaterials have found applications in pharmaceutical formulations, cosmetics, food preservation, textile processing, adhesives, coatings, ink production, and environmental remediation because of their eco-friendly nature and biodegradability (Ekwere *et al.*, 2026, Akpakpan *et al.*, 2026; Ntuen *et al.*, 2024). Tannins, for example, are useful as natural mordants and dye fixatives in textile industries, while carbohydrate-rich materials enhance adhesion and film-forming properties in paper coatings, printing and writing inks (Ntuen *et al.*, 2025). Similarly, phenolic compounds and flavonoids contribute antioxidant stability to industrial formulations (Enengedi *et al.*, 2019).

Phytochemical characterization plays an important role in determining the suitability of plant materials for industrial applications. Qualitative phytochemical analysis identifies the presence or absence of secondary metabolites, whereas quantitative analysis determines their concentrations within the material. Such analyses provide valuable information regarding the potential functional and commercial applications of natural exudates. Phytochemical-rich plant materials can serve as sustainable raw materials for the development of environmentally friendly industrial products (Sofowora, 2008; Akpakpan *et al.*, 2020).

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In addition to phytochemical screening, functional group analysis is essential for understanding the chemical behavior and physicochemical properties of natural biomaterials. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is a widely used analytical technique for identifying functional groups and molecular structures in organic substances. FTIR analysis reveals the presence of important functional groups such as hydroxyl (O–H), carbonyl (C=O), alkene (C=C), and methylene (C–H) groups, which significantly influence industrial performance characteristics including adhesion, acidity, solubility, and reactivity (Udo *et al.*, 2012). The identification of these functional groups provides insight into the possible utilization of plant exudates in the formulation of bio-based inks, adhesives, coatings, binders, and other sustainable industrial materials (Ntuen *et al.*, 2025), the physical characteristic of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate have been reported by Udo *et al.* (2016).

Despite the growing interest in sustainable biomaterials, limited information exists on the phytochemical composition and functional group characteristics of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate. Comprehensive information integrating qualitative and quantitative phytochemical composition with FTIR-based functional group characterization and their implications for sustainable industrial applications remains limited. The findings of this study may contribute to the development of renewable and environmentally friendly industrial products capable of reducing dependence on synthetic chemicals.

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Sample collection and preparation

Plant exudate was collected randomly from local pear trees (*Dacryodes edulis*) at Nsit Ikpe, in Obot Akara Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Many incisions were made on the bark of the trees and after some few minutes the exudate oozed out of the tree. The fresh exudate was

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a milky, highly viscous liquid and this was collected with help of a knife blade and dropped into a container (Udo *et al.*, 2012).

2.2 Qualitative analysis of phytochemicals

The confirmatory qualitative tests on the phytochemicals were done according to the standard procedures.

2.2.1 Test for Alkaloids

Dacryodes edulis exudate was dissolved individually in dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrates were used to test for the presence of alkaloids.

Harger's Test

Harger's reagents were added to 2 mL of filtrates. Formations of yellow precipitate showed the presence of alkaloids.

Mayer's Test

Mayer's reagent was added to 2 mL of filtrates. Formations of yellow precipitate showed the presence of alkaloid.

Wagner's Test

Wagner's reagent was added to 2 mL of filtrates. Formation of reddish brown precipitate indicated presence of alkaloids.

2.2.2 Test for Flavonoids

Lead Acetate Test

Lead acetate solution (10%) was added to small quantity of extracts and exudate respectively. Formation of yellow precipitate showed the presence of flavonoids.

Sodium Hydroxide Test

Extracts and exudates were separately treated with increasing amount of Sodium hydroxide. Formation of yellow colouration, this decolourized after addition of acid showed the presence of flavonoids.

Ferric Chloride Test

The extracts and exudates (2mL) were separately diluted with distilled water in a ratio of 1:4 and a few 3 drops of 10% ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution was added. Formation of a sustainable or blue solution indicated the presence of flavonoids.

2.2.3 Test for Saponins

Froth Test

Extracts and exudates were separately shaken vigorously with water. Formation of frothing (appearance of creamy miss of bubbles) shows that there is presence of saponin.

2.2.4 Test for Tannins

Lead Acetate Test

Lead acetate (1%) was added to 2 mL of extracts and exudates respectively. Formation of yellow precipitate showed the formation of tannins.

Ferric Chloride Test

The extracts and exudates (2mL) were separately diluted with distilled water in a ratio of 1:4 and a few 2drops of 10% ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution was added. Formation of a sustainable or blue solution indicated the presence of tannins.

2.2.5 Test for Anthraquinones

Borntrager's Test

The extracts and exudate (5 mL) were boiled separately with 10% of sulphuric acid for few minutes in water bath. It was filtered and allowed to cool. Equal volume of CHCl_3 was added to filtrate. Few drops of 10% NH_3 were added to the mixture and heated. Formation of pink colour indicated the presence of anthraquinones.

2.2.6 Test for Phenols

Ferric Chloride Test

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The extracts and exudates (10 mL) were treated separately with few drops of ferric chloride solution. Formation of bluish black colour indicated the presence of phenols.

Lead Acetate Test

The extracts and exudates (10 mL) were separately treated with few drops of lead acetate solution. Formation of yellow precipitate indicated the presence of phenols.

2.2.7 Test for Carbohydrate

Iodine Test

Dilute (0.05N) iodine solution (2 drops) was added to 2 mL of the extracts and exudates respectively. Formation of deep blue black colour which disappeared on heating and then reappeared on cooling.

Fehlings Test

About 1 mL of the extracts and exudates were boiled separately on water bath with 1mL each of Fehling solutions A and B. The colour change was observed. Formation of red precipitates indicated the presence of sugar.

Molisch Test

Molisch reagent (2 drops) was added to 5 mL of extracts and exudates respectively and mixed thoroughly. About 3 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. Formation of reddish violet ring at the junction of the two liquids indicated the presence of sugar.

2.3 Quantitative Analysis of *Dacryodes edulis* Exudate

2.3.1 Determination of Alkaloids

The Alkaloids determination was done using Harborne (1973) method. The sample of weight 1 g was placed into 250 mL beaker and 200 mL of 10% acetic acid in ethanol was added and it was covered and allowed to stand for 4 hours. It was filtered and extract was concentrated on the water bath to the quarter of the original volume. Concentrated NH₄OH was added by drop wise to the extract until precipitation was complete. The whole solution was allowed to settle and the

precipitate was collected and washed with dilute NH_4OH and then filtered. The residue is the alkaloid which was dried and weighed.

$$\% \text{ Alkaloids} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100 \quad 1$$

Where: W_1 = Weight of empty crucible; W_2 = Weight of crucible + alkaloids precipitate

2.3.2 Determination of Saponins

Exudates sample (50 mL) was placed in a 500 mL flask and 300 ml of 50% alcohol was added and boiled under reflux for 30 minutes and filtered while hot through filter paper. About 2 g of charcoal was added to the filtrate, boiled and filtered while hot. The filtrate was cooled and an equal volume of acetone was added to completely precipitate the saponin. The precipitated saponin was collected by decantation and dissolved in small amount of boiling 95% alcohol and filtered while hot. The filtrate was cooled at room temperature to separate the saponin in a relatively pure form. The clear supernatant fluid was decanted and the saponin suspended in about 20 mL of alcohol was filtered. The filter paper was transferred to a dessicator containing anhydrous calcium chloride and left to dry and then weighed (El-Olemy *et al.*, 1994).

2.3.3 Determination of Tannins

Exudate sample 500 mg was weighed into 100 mL plastic bottle. 50 mL of distilled water was shaken for one hour in a mechanical shaker. This was filtered into a 50 mL volumetric flask and made to the mark. The 5 mL of the filtrate was pipette out into tube and mixed with 3 mL of 0.1 FeCl_3 in 0.1N HCl and 0.008M potassium ferrocyanide. The absorbance was measured in a spectrophotometer at 120nm wavelengths, within 10 minutes (Van –Burden and Robinson, 1981).

2.3.4 Determination of Phenol

The exudate sample was boiled with 50 mL of ether for the extraction of the phenolic component for 15 minutes and 5 mL of the exudate was pipetted into 50 mL flask, and then 10 mL of distilled water was added. 2 ml of NH_4OH solution and 5 mL of concentrated amyl alcohol were

also added. The sample was made up to mark and left to react for 30 minutes for colour development. This was read at 505 nm (El-Olemy *et al.*, 1994).

2.3.5 Determination of Carbohydrate

Exudate sample (100 mg) was hydrolysed in boiling tube with 5 mL of 2.5 N HCl in a boiling water bath for a period of 3 hours. It was cooled at room temperature and solid sodium carbonate was added until effervescence ceases. The content was centrifuged and the supernatant was made to 100 ml by using distilled water. From this 0.2 mL of sample was pipetted out and made up to the volume of 1 ml with phenol reagent, followed by addition of 5 mL of sulphuric acid. The test tubes were kept at 25-30°C for 20 minutes. The absorbance was read at 490 nm (Krishnaveni *et al.*, 1984).

2.3.6 Determination of functional groups

The functional group of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate were determined using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). KBr disks containing 1 % finely ground samples were used.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Phytochemicals in the *Dacryodes edulis* Exudate

The presence or absence of phytochemicals is indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Phytochemicals in the *Dacryodes edulis* exudate (qualitative)

Phytochemical	Results
Alkaloids	
a. Mayer's reagent	+++
b. Tannic acid	+++
c. Wagner's reagent	+++
Saponin (Froth)	+++
Flavanoid	
a. FeCl ₃	++
b. NaOH	++
c. Lead acetate	++

Tannin	
a. FeCl ₃	++
Carbohydrate (CHO)	
a. Fehling solution	+
b. Iodine	+++
Anthraquinone	-
Phenol	
a. FeCl ₃	++

+ = Present in minor quantity; ++ = Present in moderate quantity; +++ = Present in higher quantity; - = Not detected.

Alkaloids, saponin, tannin, phenol, flavanoid and carbohydrate were found to be present in the exudates while anthroquinone was absent.

Table 2 Phytochemicals in the *Dacryodes edulis* exudates (quantitative)

Phytochemicals	Concentration
Alkaloids (mg/100g)	0.0208 ± 0.0004
Tannins (mg/100g)	0.04789 ± 0.0055
Phenol (mg/100g)	0.0103 ± 0.0003
Carbohydrate (mg/100g)	36.5294 ± 0.0000
Flavanoid (mg/100g)	0.0397 ± 0.0004
Saponin (mg/100g)	0.0090 ± 0.0001

The phytochemicals present in *Dacryodes edulis* exudate were quantified as presented in Table 2.

The phytochemical profile of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate revealed that it is a promising natural resource for medicinal and environmentally friendly industrial applications. Qualitative analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and carbohydrates,

while anthraquinones were absent. Quantitative analysis further showed that carbohydrates were the most abundant constituent (36.5294 mg/100 g), whereas alkaloids (0.0208 mg/100 g), flavonoids (0.0397 mg/100 g), tannins (0.04789 mg/100 g), phenols (0.0103 mg/100 g), and saponins (0.0090 mg/100 g) were present in measurable amounts.

The high occurrence of alkaloids in the exudate suggests that the exudate may possess antimicrobial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antimalarial properties, since many naturally occurring alkaloids exhibit these pharmacological activities (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). Flavonoids and phenolic compounds are well-known antioxidants capable of scavenging free radicals, thereby reducing oxidative stress associated with chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular disorders (Enengedi *et al.*, 2019; Pereira *et al.*, 2024).. The presence of tannins further supports the traditional use of the plant in wound healing, as tannins exhibit antimicrobial, astringent, and anti-inflammatory activities that promote tissue repair and inhibit microbial growth (Akpakpan *et al.*, 2026, Akpan *et al.*, 2017; Akpabio *et al.*, 2012b). Saponins have also been reported to possess immunomodulatory, antifungal, antibacterial, cholesterol-lowering, and anticancer properties, making the exudate a potential source of bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical development (Ramoithloa *et al.*, 2025; Kafi *et al.*, 2026; Akpan *et al.*, 2017).

The high carbohydrate content indicates that the exudate is rich in natural polysaccharides or gum-like substances. These materials can serve as biodegradable binders, stabilizers, emulsifiers, and controlled-release matrices in pharmaceutical formulations (Ntuen *et al.*, 2024). Such natural polymers are increasingly preferred over synthetic excipients because of their low toxicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability (Akpakpan *et al.*, 2026).

From the perspective of sustainable industrial relevance, the phytochemical composition makes *D. edulis* exudate an attractive renewable biomaterial (Udo *et al.*, 2012). The abundance of

carbohydrates suggests its suitability for producing eco-friendly adhesives, biodegradable films, hydrogels, coatings, and packaging materials. Natural gums obtained from plant exudates are increasingly replacing petroleum-derived polymers in sustainable manufacturing (Valverde, 2013).

The antioxidant phenolics and flavonoids may also be exploited as natural preservatives in food, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical industries, reducing dependence on synthetic antioxidants such as *Butylated Hydroxytoluene* (BHT) and *Butylated Hydroxyanisole* (BHA) (Nawaz *et al.*, 2020) Enengedi *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, the antimicrobial activity associated with alkaloids, tannins, and saponins could be utilized in the formulation of sustainable disinfectants, antimicrobial coatings, herbal soaps, cosmetics, and food packaging systems that inhibit microbial contamination (Yukseket *et al.*, 2025; Enengedi *et al.*, 2018; Uko, *et al.*, 2017)

Furthermore, the biodegradable nature of the exudate makes it suitable for environmental applications, including the development of bio-based adsorbents for wastewater treatment, biodegradable composites, and environmentally benign coating materials (Yukseket *et al.*, 2025; Ekwere, 2026). The use of renewable plant-derived materials in these applications such as exudate can contribute to reducing environmental pollution and minimizing the health risks associated with persistent contaminants in aquatic ecosystems (Akpan *et al.*, 2022). Such applications align with the principles of sustainable chemistry by utilizing renewable plant resources, minimizing hazardous chemicals, and reducing environmental pollution. The phytochemical composition of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate highlights its significant potential as a sustainable source of bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical applications and as a renewable raw material for sustainable industrial products.

3.2 Functional group analysis

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The IR spectrum of the purified *Dacryodes edulis* exudates sample is presented Figure 1 and interpreted in Table 3.

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate

The FTIR spectrum of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate reveals a complex mixture of oxygenated and hydrocarbon-containing phytochemicals. The broad absorption at 3369 cm⁻¹ corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations of hydroxyl groups, suggesting the presence of alcohols and phenolic compounds (Akpakpan *et al.*, 2023). This agrees with the phytochemical screening, which detected phenols, flavonoids, tannins, and carbohydrates. Hydroxyl groups are important because they contribute to antioxidant activity through hydrogen donation and free radical.

The intense bands at 2922 and 2870 cm⁻¹ are attributed to asymmetric and symmetric C–H stretching vibrations of methylene and methyl groups, respectively (Faix *et al.*, 1992). These peaks are characteristic of long aliphatic hydrocarbon chains commonly found in natural resins, waxes, and terpenoids (Shaheen *et al.*, 2022) Their presence suggests that the exudate possesses hydrophobic components that can contribute to film-forming and adhesive properties

The absorption at 1707 cm^{-1} corresponds to carbonyl (C=O) stretching vibrations, indicating the presence of esters, aldehydes, ketones, or carboxylic acids (Ali *et al.*, 2020). Carbonyl-containing compounds often exhibit high chemical reactivity and can participate in polymerization, esterification, and cross-linking reactions, making them valuable in industrial processing.

Table 3: FTIR Interpretation of *Dacryodes edulis* Exudate

Peak (cm^{-1})	Functional Group	Bond Vibration	Possible Phytochemical Source	Significance
3369.5	O–H	Stretching	Phenols, alcohols, carbohydrates	Indicates hydroxyl-rich compounds responsible for antioxidant activity and hydrogen bonding.
3071.3	=C–H	Aromatic/alkene stretching	Aromatic phenolics, flavonoids	Aromatic unsaturated compounds present
2922.2	C–H	Asymmetric stretching	Alkanes, long-chain hydrocarbons, terpenoids	Characteristic of hydrocarbon chains in plant resins and essential oils.
2870.1	C–H	Symmetric stretching	Methyl and methylene groups	Indicates aliphatic components present in the exudate.
2091.0	C≡C / C≡N (weak)	Stretching	Trace unsaturated compounds	Weak band; may indicate minor unsaturated constituents.
1707.1	C=O	Carbonyl stretching	Esters, aldehydes, ketones, carboxylic acids	Suggests oxygenated compounds contributing to chemical reactivity.
1640.0	C=C	Aromatic C=C stretching	Flavonoids, phenolics	Indicates aromatic structures and possible bound moisture.
1453.7	CH ₂	Bending (scissoring)	Lipids, terpenoids	Characteristic of aliphatic chains.
1379.1	CH ₃	Symmetric bending	Alkanes	Indicates methyl substitution.
1271.0	C–O	Stretching	Phenols, esters	Oxygen-containing phytochemicals present.
1203.9	C–O–C	Stretching	Ethers, esters	Suggests glycosidic or ether linkages.
1136.8	C–O	Stretching	Alcohols,	Characteristic of carbohydrates and

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Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Bond Vibration	Possible Phytochemical Source	Significance
1098.4	C–O	Stretching	polysaccharides Secondary alcohols	gums. Indicates polysaccharide backbone.
1047.4	C–O	Stretching	Polysaccharides, carbohydrates	Strong evidence of natural gum/carbohydrate materials.
991.5	=C–H	Out-of-plane bending	Alkenes	Indicates unsaturated structures.
879.7	C–H	Aromatic bending	Aromatic compounds	Supports aromatic phytochemicals.
790.2	C–H	Aromatic out-of-plane bending	Benzene derivatives	Indicates substituted aromatic rings.

The band at 1640 cm^{-1} is assigned to aromatic C=C stretching and may also include contributions from absorbed water molecules. This supports the presence of aromatic phytochemicals such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which are known for their antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties (Sutariya, *et al.*, 2023).

The fingerprint region ($1454\text{--}790\text{ cm}^{-1}$) contains several absorption bands associated with C–O, C–O–C, CH₂, and aromatic C–H vibrations (Shaheen *et al.*, 2022.). These bands indicate the presence of carbohydrates, ethers, esters, and polysaccharides, which are characteristic constituents of natural plant gums and exudates. The strong absorptions at 1137, 1098, and 1047 cm^{-1} particularly indicate polysaccharide structures responsible for viscosity, emulsification, and gel-forming abilities (Ntuen *et al.*, 2024).

3.3 Sustainable Industrial Relevance of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate

The FTIR results demonstrate that *Dacryodes edulis* exudate has considerable potential for sustainable and industrial applications.

Table 4: Sustainable industrial relevance of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate

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Functional Group	Industrial Relevance
Hydroxyl (O–H)	Production of natural antioxidants, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, hydrogels, biodegradable polymers, and hydrogen-bonded adhesives.
Carbonyl (C=O)	Useful in polymer synthesis, resin curing, cross-linking reactions, coatings, adhesives, and biodegradable plastics.
Aromatic phenolics	Development of natural preservatives, antimicrobial agents, antioxidants, food additives, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical formulations.
Aliphatic hydrocarbons	Manufacture of natural waxes, sealants, waterproof coatings, lubricants, and bio-based resin materials.
C–O and C–O–C groups	Production of natural gums, thickeners, emulsifiers, stabilizers, edible coatings, biodegradable films, and controlled drug-delivery matrices.
Polysaccharides	Applications in paper, textile, food, pharmaceutical, and biodegradable packaging industries.

Conclusion

This study successfully investigated the phytochemical constituents and functional group characteristics of *Dacryodes edulis* exudate with a view to assessing its suitability for sustainable industrial applications. The qualitative phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important bioactive compounds including alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and carbohydrates, while anthraquinones were absent. Quantitative analysis further revealed that the exudate contains appreciable amounts of these phytochemicals, particularly carbohydrates and tannins, which are known to possess adhesive, dye-binding, antioxidant, and industrially useful properties. FTIR spectroscopic analysis identified significant functional groups such as hydroxyl (O–H), carbonyl (C=O), alkene (C=C), methylene, and alkane groups, indicating the presence of alcohols, carboxylic acids, and unsaturated compounds within the exudate. The presence of

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tannins and hydroxyl-containing compounds indicates that *Dacryodes edulis* exudate may serve as a useful natural mordant, binder, adhesive, and eco-friendly raw material in the production of inks, coatings, textiles, and related industrial products. The study therefore demonstrates that *Dacryodes edulis* exudate has considerable potential as a renewable and biodegradable biomaterial capable of reducing dependence on synthetic and environmentally hazardous industrial chemicals. Further studies on its physicochemical performance, bioactivity, stability, toxicity, and large-scale industrial applications are recommended

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